

Effect of Terminal Heat Stress in Wheat: An Overview

Sougata Roy¹ and Sourik Poddar^{2*}

¹M.Sc. Scholar, Dept. of Agronomy, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi-110012, India

²Ph.D Scholar, Dept. of Genetics and Plant Breeding, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Mohanpur-741252, Nadia, West Bengal, India

*Corresponding author. E-mail: sourikpoddar1997@gmail.com

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), is the most famous grain crop grown by the vast majority of the world's population mainly in western Asia, America, Australia. Common bread wheat is accepted by more than 2 billion people worldwide as a staple food. Wheat produces about 55% of all carbs and 20% of all dietary calories in the globe (Nikos and Jelle, 2012). Wheat output reached 772.64 million tonnes in 2020-21, covering more land area than any other commercial food (220.4 million hectares in 2019) (FAO, 2019). It is the second most extensively cultivated crop, behind maize (1.03 billion tonnes) and before rice (500 million tonnes) (www.fao.org). Wheat and other grain output have quadrupled globally since 1960, and this trend is anticipated to continue throughout the twenty-first century (Shiferaw *et al.*, 2013).

Abiotic stress and crop productivity

Abiotic stress is defined as the external non-living elements (stressors) that have a negative impact on an organism's physiological processes. Long-term unresolved physiological stress can disrupt the organism's balance, resulting in harmful or pathological consequences, like direct sunlight, high winds velocity, extreme temperatures (low as well as high), drought, flooding, and saline stress in saline soil. Drought, heat, cold, and salt are key abiotic stressors that hinder crops from attaining their maximum yield potential, decreasing agricultural output for the world's key crop plants (Al-Khatib and Paulsen, 1990). These abiotic stressors are linked, with changes in the expression of a collection of genes causing reactions that impact growth rates and production.

Heat stress in wheat

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC 2014) assessment, global mean temperature would rise by 0.3°C every decade over current levels, resulting in around 0.3°C and 10°C for the years 2025 and 2100, respectively (Hossain *et al.*, 2013). Interactions between genotypes and their environment have an impact on a genotype's overall performance (Dia *et al.*, 2016). In cool-season cereal species, heat stress promotes physiological changes by lowering chlorophyll content, which leads to leaf senescence (Almeselmani *et al.*, 2011; Dhyani *et al.*, 2013). Wheat grain filling can be slowed by high temperatures (> 31°C) after anthesis (Al-Khatib and Paulsen 1990; Stone *et al.*, 1995; Wardlaw and Moncur 1995). Heat stress reduces photosynthetic capacity (Almeselmani *et al.*, 2012; Ashraf and Harris, 2013), changes plant water relations (Hasanuzzaman *et al.*, 2012, 2013), hormonal changes (Krasensky and Jonak, 2012), decreases metabolic activities (Farooq *et al.*, 2011), production of oxidative reactive species (Wang *et al.*, 2011, 2012, 2014, 2016), increases pollen mortality (Oshino *et al.*, 2011). Plant development, grain quality, and yield are all negatively affected by rapid temperature rise during grain filling duration (GFD).

Sudden temperature rise during GFD is a key constraint on wheat yield in many settings (Hays *et al.*, 2007). Heat stress has affected 36 million hectares of land worldwide, with the majority of this land in South Asia (Reynolds *et al.*, 2001). Heat stress affects 13.5 ha⁻¹ (Joshi *et al.*, 2007a) of land in

India. The eastern Gangetic plains encompass eastern Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Jharkhand, and West Bengal, whereas central and peninsular India encompasses MP, Maharashtra, and Karnataka, and Bangladesh is regarded as a hotspot in south Asia. The Indo-Gangetic plain's north-western reaches are classified as a moderate heat stress zone (Joshi *et al.*, 2007b; Singh *et al.*, 2007). The rate of grain filling was affected by the increase in temperature after anthesis (Stone and Nikolas, 1994). The shape and size of grain are altered by a short-term (3-4 days) abrupt temperature rise in the form of a heatwave (35-37°C) (Wardlaw and Wrigley, 1994). Short-term (4-day) heat exposure (>35°C) reduces yield by up to 23%, and 3-day heat treatment (38°C from 8 a.m. to 5 p.m.) reduces individual yield component by up to 28.3% (Stone and Nikolas, 1994). India is experiencing severe heat stress (Rane *et al.*, 2007; Joshi *et al.*, 2007b) as shown in Fig 1. Wheat yield losses were enhanced by global warming in the form of climate change (Lillemo *et al.*, 2005). When compared to tropical cereals, temperate cereals are more susceptible to rising temperatures. The use of molecular markers to investigate the genetic basis of thermotolerance is a promising technique (Maestri *et al.*, 2002). Because of the difficulties in phenotypic selection for tolerance and the overall complexity of abiotic stress tolerance, marker aided selection (MAS) has been proposed as a beneficial strategy for developing crop stress resistance. On the other hand, Akpinar *et al.*, (2017) used genomic (Fig 2) and transcriptome techniques to map 68, 592 SNPs from the *Aegilops tauschii* genotype MvGB589 onto chromosome 5D. To compensate for the genetic deconstruction of wheat kernel size and form, high temperatures accelerate the pace of grain filling.

Fig 1: Temperature departure (source: USDA)

Fig 2: Wheat genome (source: science.org)

Mechanism of heat tolerance in wheat

Heat avoidance, heat tolerance, and heat escape processes are three separate methods that crops use to adapt to heat stress situations. Leaf rolling, waxiness in heat avoidance, stress-responsive gene synthesis for tolerance, and altering the phenology of plants once they detect heat stress to escape are some of the measures. In cereals, there is no one 'thermotolerant' gene that controls heat tolerance. At different periods of the life cycle and in different tissues, distinct components of tolerance regulated by different sets of genes are necessary for heat tolerance. Hormones are thought to regulate every element of plant metabolism (Slisbury *et al.*, 1992). When plants are heat-stressed during the vegetative development phase, among other biological processes, it changes hormone homeostasis. Abscisic acid (ABA) induction can be a significant component of thermotolerance in situations where heat and drought stress occur frequently and concurrently. Gibberellins have the opposite impact on high-temperature tolerance as ABA.

Relationship between grain filling rate and duration

Because heat stress speeds up the rate of grain filling, the time it takes to fill the grain is reduced (Dias and Lidon, 2009). Because the availability of photo-assimilates may be limited under these conditions, a 5°C rise in temperature above 20°C for 12 days enhanced the pace of grain filling and decreased the grain filling time in wheat (Yin *et al.*, 2009; Calderini *et al.*, 2006).

Agronomic trait

Temperature increases have a significant impact on grain weight and quantity (Ferris *et al.*, 1998). Saini and Aspinall (1982); Thorne and Wood (1987); Tashiro and Wardlaw (1990); Mitchell *et al.*, (1993); Wheeler *et al.*, (1996b) have all reported ovule abortion owing to high temperatures. High temperatures during anthesis reduced grain counts per spike in winter wheat 'Hereward,' according to Wheeler *et al.*, (1996a). Low grain fertility was generated by exposure to high temperature for as little as 1°C during key intervals between booting and anthesis, according to Saini and Aspinall (1982).

According to Ferris *et al.* (1998), a four-day rise in maximum temperatures around anthesis influences grain number, resulting in a direct reduction in grain yield at maturity. The number of grains per spike is inversely proportional to the length of heat stress (Rawson and Bagga, 1979). High temperatures (>30°C) during floret development can induce total sterility (Saini and Aspinall, 1982). Wheat yield loss can be increased by one degree if the standard temperature rises by one degree during the reproductive period (Bennett *et al.*, 2012; Yu *et al.*, 2014).

Yield

Grain yield has been found to be reduced by 50% when high temperatures are integrated (i.e., total thermal time over 31°C during 8 days of treatment during anthesis) (Ferris *et al.*, 1998). During grain loading, each 1°C increase over the optimal temperature (15–20°C) reduces yields by 3–4% (Wardlaw *et al.*, 1989). When exposed to 32–38°C temperature during the basic grain formation stage in India, most commercially cultivated wheat cultivars lost roughly 50% of their yield, which may be computed using this factor (3–4% loss each 1°C above 15–20°C). According to Ferris *et al.*, (1998) and Huang *et al.*, (2012), greater temperatures can have negative impacts on root development, posing a further danger to crop productivity.

Conclusion

Heat stress in wheat is becoming more common because of rising temperatures across the world. Heat stress has a significant impact on grain setting time and pace, resulting in a loss in grain yields. Heat stress may be mitigated by creating resistant genotypes and agronomic methods. Despite the fact that the physiological foundation of heat tolerance in wheat is well recognized, more study into phenotypic plasticity and assimilate partitioning is needed. Traditional breeding combined with contemporary biotechnological technologies for the discovery and introgression of heat tolerance genes into elite lines is a significant field for future research. The most recent genomics resource, along with ecophysiological research, may be valuable for understanding genotypes and their interactions with the environment.

Reference

- Akpinar BA, S Lucas and H Budak. 2017. A largescale chromosome specific SNP discovery guideline. *Functional Integrated Genomics* 17(1):97–105.
- Al-Khatib K and GM Paulsen. 1990. Photosynthesis and productivity during high temperature stress of wheat genotypes from major world regions. *Crop Science* 30:1127–132.

- Almeselmani M, F Abdullah, F Hareri, M Naesan, MA Ammar and OZ Kanbar. 2011. Effect of drought on different physiological characters and yield component in different Syrian durum wheat varieties. *Journal of Agricultural Science* 3:127-33.
- Almeselmani M, PS Deshmukh and V Chinnusamy. 2012. Effect of prolonged high temperature stress on respiration, photosynthesis and gene expression in wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) varieties differing in their thermotolerance. *Plant Stress* 6:25-32.
- Ashraf M and PJC Harris. 2013. Photosynthesis under stressful environments: an overview. *Photosynthetica* 51:163-190.
- Bennett D, Aizanloo, M Reynolds, H Kuchel, P Langridge and T Schnurbusch. 2012. Genetic dissection of grain yield and physical grain quality in bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) under water limited environments. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 125:255-271.
- Calderini DF, MP Reynolds and GA Slafer. 2006. Source-sink effects on grain weight of bread wheat, durum wheat and triticale at different locations. *Australian Journal of Agricultural Research* 57:227-233.
- Dhyani K, MW Ansari, YR Rao, RS Verma, A Shukla and N Tuteja. 2013. Comparative physiological response of wheat genotypes under terminal heat stress. *Plant Signaling and Behavior* 8(6):245-264
- Dia M, TC Wehner, R Hassell, DS Price, GE Boyhan et al. 2016. Genotype × environment interaction and stability analysis for watermelon fruit yield in the United States. *Crop Science* 56:1645-1661.
- Dias AS and FC Lidon. 2009. Evaluation of grain filling rate and duration in bread and durum wheat, under heat stress after anthesis. *Journal of Agronomy and Crop Science* 195:137-147.
- Farooq M, H Bramley, JA Palta and KHM Siddique. 2011. Heat stress in wheat during reproductive and grain-filling phases. *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences* 30:491-507.
- Ferris. R, RH Ellis, TR Wheeler and P Hadley. 1998. Effect of high temperature stress at anthesis on grain yield and biomass of field-grown crops of wheat. *Annals of Botany* 82:631-639.
- Hasanuzzaman M, K Naha, MM Alam, R Roychowdhury and M Fujita. 2013. Physiological, biochemical, and molecular mechanisms of heat stress tolerance in plants. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 14:9643-9684.
- Hasanuzzaman M, MA Hossain, JAT da Silva and M Fujita. 2012. Plant responses and tolerance to abiotic oxidative stress: antioxidant defenses is a key factor. Terminal heat tolerance in wheat: An overview 11 In: Bandi V, Shanker AK, Shanker C, Mandapaka M (eds) *Crop stress and its management: perspectives and strategies*. Springer Berlin, pp 261-31
- Hays DB, JH Do, RE Mason, G Morgan and SA Finlayson. 2007. Heat stress induced ethylene production in developing wheat grains induces kernel abortion and increased maturation in a susceptible cultivar. *Plant Science* 172:1113-1123.
- Hossain A, MAZ Sarker, M Saifuzzaman, JA Teixeira da Silva, MV Lozovskaya and MM Akhter. 2013. Evaluation of growth, yield, relative performance and heat susceptibility of eight wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) genotypes grown under heat stress. *International Journal Plant Production* 7:615-636
- Huang B, S Rachmilevitch and J Xu. 2012. Root carbon and protein metabolism associated with heat tolerance. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 63:3455- 3465.

- IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change). 2014. Summary for policymakers. In: Stocker TF, Qin D, Plattner GK, Tignor M, Allen SK, Boschung J, Nauels A, Xia Y, Bex V, Midgley PM (eds) Climate change 2013: the physical science basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge
- Joshi AK, B Mishra, R Chatrath, G Ortiz Ferrara and RP Singh. 2007b. Wheat improvement in India: present status, emerging challenges and future prospects. *Euphytica* 157: 431-446.
- Joshi AK, R Chand, B Arun, R Singh and G Ortiz Ferrara. 2007a. Breeding crops for reduced – tillage management in the intensive, rice-wheat systems of south Asia. *Euphytica* 153:135-151.
- Krasensky J and C Jonak. 2012. Drought, salt, and temperature stress-induced metabolic rearrangements and regulatory networks. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 63:1593-1608.
- Lillemo M, M van, Ginkel, RM Trethowan, E Hernandez and J Crossa. 2005. Differential adaptation of CIMMYT bread wheat to global high temperature environments. *Crop Science* 45:2443-2453.
- 104.Lim PO, HJ Kim and HG Nam. 2007. Leaf senescence. *Annual Review of Plant Biology* 58:115-136.
- Maestri E, N Klueva, C Perrotta, M Gulli, HT Nguyen and N Marmioli. 2002. Molecular genetics of heat tolerance and heat shock proteins in cereals. *Plant Molecular Biology* 48:667-681.
- Mitchell RAC, VJ Mitchell, SP Driscoll, J Franklin and DLawlor. 1993. Effects of increased CO₂ concentration and temperature on growth and yield of winter wheat at two levels of nitrogen application. *Plant Cell Environment* 16:521-529.
- Nikos A, Jelle B. World agriculture towards 2030/2050: The 2012 revision. ESA Working Paper No. 12-03. Rome: Food and Agriculture; 2012
- Oshino T, S Miura, S Kikuchi, K Hamada, K Yano, M Watanabe and A Higashitani. 2011. Auxin depletion in barley plants under high-temperature conditions represses DNA proliferation in organelles and nuclei via transcriptional alterations. *Plant Cell Environment* 34:284-290.
- Rane J, RK Pannu, VS Sohu, RS Saini, B Mishra, J Shoran, J Crossa, M Vargas and AK Joshi. 2007. Performance of yield and stability of advanced wheat genotypes under heat stressed environments of IndoGangetic Plains. *Crop Science* 47:1561-1573.
- Rawson HM and AK Bagga. 1979. Influence of temperature between floral initiation and flag leaf emergence on grain number in wheat. *Australian Journal of Plant Physiology* 6:391-400.
- Reynolds MP, JI Ortiz-Monasterio and A Mc Nab. 2001. Application of physiology in wheat breeding. CIMMYT, El Batan, Mexico. http://www.cimmyt.org/research/wheat/map/research_results/wphysio/wphysio_contents.pdf.
- Saini HS and D Aspinall. 1982. Abnormal sporogenesis in wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) induced by short periods of high temperature. *Annals of Botany* 49:835–846.
- Salisbury, F. B. and Ross, C. W. 1992 . Plant physiology. 4th edn. pp. 357–548. Wadsworth: Belmont, CA, USA.
- Shiferaw B, Smale M, Braun HJ, Duveiller E, Reynolds M, Muricho G. Crops that feed the world 10. Past successes and future challenges to the role played by wheat in global food security. *Food Security*. 2013;5:291-317. DOI: 10.1007/s12571-013-0263-y
- Singh RP, J Huerta-Espino, RC Sharma, AK Joshi and R Trethowan. 2007. High yielding spring wheat germplasm for global irrigated and rainfed production systems. *Euphytica* 157:351-363.

- Stone PJ and ME Nicolas. 1994. Wheat cultivars vary widely in responses of grain yield and quality to short period of post-anthesis heat stress. *Australian Journal of Plant Physiology* 21:887-900.
- Stone PJ, R Savin, IF Wardlaw and ME Nicolas. 1995. The influence of recovery temperature on the effects of a brief heat shock on wheat. I. Grain growth. *Australian Journal of Plant Physiology* 22:945-954.
- Tashiro T and IF Wardlaw. 1990. The response to high temperature shock and humidity changes prior to and during the early stages of grain development in wheat. *Australian Journal of Plant Physiology* 17:551-561.
- Thorne GN and DW Wood. 1987. Effects of radiation and temperature on tiller survival, grain number and grain yield in winter wheat. *Annals of Botany* 59:413-426.
- Wang H, H Wang, H Shao and X Tang. 2016. Recent advances in utilizing transcription factors to improve plant abiotic stress tolerance by transgenic technology. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 7:67.
- Wang X, J Cai, D Jiang, F Liu, T Dai and W Cao. 2011. Pre-anthesis high-temperature acclimation alleviates damage to the flag leaf caused by post-anthesis heat stress in wheat. *Journal of Plant Physiology* 168:585-593.
- Wang X, J Cai, F Liu, M Jin, H Yu, D Jiang, B Wollenweber, T Dai and W Cao. 2012. Pre-anthesis high temperature acclimation alleviates the negative effects of post-anthesis heat stress on stem stored carbohydrates remobilization and grain starch accumulation in wheat. *Journal of Cereal Science* 55:331-336.
- Wang X, J Cai, F Liu, T Dai, W Cao, B Wollenweber and D Jiang. 2014. Multiple heat priming enhances thermo-tolerance to a later high temperature stress via improving subcellular antioxidant activities in wheat seedlings. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry* 74:185-192.
- Wardlaw IF and CW Wrigley 1994. Heat tolerance in temperate cereals: An overview. *Australian Journal of Plant Physiology* 21:695-703.
- Wardlaw IF and L Moncur. 1995. The response of wheat to high temperature following anthesis. I. The rate and duration of kernel filling. *Australian Journal of Plant Physiology* 22:391-397.
- Wardlaw IF, IA Dawson, P Munibi and R Fewster. 1989. The tolerance of wheat to high temperatures during reproductive growth. I. Survey procedures and general response patterns. *Australian Journal of Agricultural Research* 40:1-13.
- Wheeler TR, GR Batts, RH Ellis, JIL Morrison and P Hadley. 1996b. Growth and yield of winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) crops in response to CO₂ and temperature. *Journal of Agricultural Science* 127:37-48.
- Wheeler TR, TD Hong, RH Ellis, GR Batts, JIL Morrison and P Hadley. 1996a. The duration and rate of grain growth, and harvest index, of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) in response to temperature and carbon dioxide. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 47:623-630.
- Yin X, W Guo and JH Spiertz. 2009. A quantitative approach to characterize sink-source relationships during grain filling in contrasting wheat genotypes. *Field Crops Research* 114: 119-126
- Yu Q, L Li, Q Luo, D Eamus, S Xu, C Chen, E Wang, J Liu and DC Nielsen. 2014. Year patterns of climate impact on wheat yields. *International Journal of Climatology* 34:518-528.